

Spatial microsimulation for residential energy consumption, a case study of Scotland

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Abstract.

Detailed, integrated data on energy consumption, housing characteristics, and socioeconomic conditions are essential to address fuel poverty and to meet the UK Net Zero Agenda. However, policy action is constrained by the limited availability of fine-grained spatial data, as energy-relevant household information is often private or restricted.

Using machine learning and spatial data analysis, we combine a spatial data base with heights and footprints of residential buildings, the detailed but incomplete Energy Performance Certificate database with official area totals from the Output Area Aggregates of the 2022 Census to recreate a household-level representation of Scotland's residential energy landscape, allowing to study energy consumption patterns at a previously unavailable level of detail.

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1 Introduction

Rising energy prices have become a critical challenge for UK households, directly impacting living standards and welfare. One of the main indices for the relationship between energy costs and household well-being is fuel poverty, which in Scotland is defined as spending over

10% of income on energy. Currently, fuel poverty affects approximately 34% of Scottish households (Scottish Government 2024).

Simultaneously, the UK's Net Zero Agenda is intensifying pressure on the domestic sector, which in UK is one of the older stock of houses from Europe, therefore highly energy consuming. The residential sector accounts for 13.4% of UK greenhouse gas emissions (Climate Change Committee 2025). Addressing both fuel poverty and decarbonisation requires a household-level understanding of the quality of the building residential environment. Unfortunately, fine-grained housing data that would support this goal are typically aggregated, outdated, or inaccessible due to privacy constraints.

Spatial microsimulation can overcome these limitations by integrating census aggregates and microdata samples to generate synthetic representations of the real households or individuals (Birkin 2021). This study asks: Can spatial microsimulation create reliable household-level datasets for studying energy consumption in Scotland? Which is the optimal scale to produce it?

An energy relevant household level data base requires detailed information on building age, type of building and heating fuel. In England and Wales, representative microdata with metered consumption enables household-level spatial microsimulation of energy consumption (Ruchi Choudhary et al. 2022) but comparable datasets do not exist for Scotland. Alternatively, EPC data include several energy-relevant variables, and are openly available in Scotland, however spatial consistency and representativeness are questionable since only properties sold or rented since 2009 are included (Scottish Government 2008).

Our study overcomes these data constraints by taking advantage of the spatial autocorrelation present in nearby buildings, meaning properties within the same geographical area or neighbourhood tend to share similar characteristics: building age, property type (Fleischmann et al. 2025; Garbasevski et al. 2021). We generate synthetic housing data using the Census OA aggregates (Scotland’s Census 2022) and EPC data (Scottish Government 2025) through integerisation (Lovell, Ballas, and Watson 2014) and spatially explicit KNN (Deppner and Cajias 2024), producing a representative spatial microdata set capturing energy-relevant dwelling characteristics at household resolution for Scotland.

This methodological pipeline enables multi-scale data integration while preserving statistical consistency with the official aggregated values. Following validation and calibration, the resulting synthetic population data provides a baseline for agent-based modelling and exploratory policy simulations to assess local interventions.

2 Data and method

2.1 Data

This study includes two different data sources: The 2022 Census OA aggregates (Scotland’s Census 2022) provide official census aggregates of housing characteristics at the aggregation of 25 to 89 households, the smaller census block. The EPC (Scottish Government 2025) register provides energy characteristics of every property sold or rented since 2009.

2.2 Method

An average of 70% of the households per each Output Area in Scotland have an EPC, 0.6% of Output Areas in Scotland have no Energy Performance Certificates at all, and while present in all the territory, the distribution and completeness of this data base varies significantly across the country (Map1). This approach is grounded in the principle of spatial autocorrelation and assumes that geographically proximate dwellings of the same property type share key structural characteristics, particularly building age, total floor area and main heating fuel. A confirmation of the importance of spatial autocorrelation can be seen in the Random Forest variable-importance in figure 2 where Data Zone, postcode and Output Area are all important variables for predicting the building age.

Map 1 – Percentage of households with an available Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) at the Data Zone level (500–1,000 households) in Scotland. Coverage is nearly complete nationwide. However, data is relatively scarcer in urban areas due to high housing density and older stock, while larger, less dense areas show higher coverage. Darker areas typically represent newer developments built after EPCs became mandatory.

To move from a biased, market-dynamic based EPC database to a representative stock of houses, the data fusion pipeline first restricts the EPC records to those up to date for each property, excluding historical certificates. The pipeline then harmonises the variables shared across datasets. In particular, the census accommodation type is reclassified to ensure consistency with EPC categories by combining the EPC property type and built form variables into the accommodation type category from the census.

This harmonisation step enables the construction of calibration weights that adjust the EPC microdata to align with census marginal totals.

For each OA and property category, a weight is computed as the ratio between the census target count and the corresponding EPC existent count, as a representation of how representative the EPC is in that Output Area. Integerisation converts those fractional weights into integer replications of EPC records, distributing the remaining households based on the largest fractional remainders and producing the target total households from the census. This is a common approach to minimize

distortion and match the census total for each OA.

Figure 2 - Random Forest variable importance to predict building age. Ranking and relative size exposes which features the model relies on the most to infer building age.

When an OA lacks EPC records for a required property category, EPC information is borrowed from the set of nearest OAs, identified using centroid-based distances through a spatial KNN framework. The matching EPC records, therefore, act as borrowers of information for the target OA lacking building data for that property category (Figure 2).

4. Results & discussion

Our spatial pipeline produces an energy-relevant synthetic stock of houses at OA scale. This spatial unit contains between 25 and 89 households within a relatively homogeneous geographic space, where inter-building variability is sufficiently low to allow accurate reproduction of the housing stock using available EPC, which on average are 17 per OA for the residential sector in Scotland.

The resulting dataset achieves a mean RMSE of 3.54 dwellings in household counts, an average error of 6.37% in building type per OA. To reduce the error of inaccurate extrapolation of EPC attributes, we impose spatial constraints when selecting donor EPCs and restrict the transferred EPC variables to those likely to vary little across OA.

The result is a database that is already connected with the official Census count, therefore working as a baseline to

Figure 1 - Combining a detailed but incomplete sample with official area totals, adjusting the sample to match those totals, and filling missing categories using nearby similar cases. Ia generated.

allocate synthetic individuals that carry demographic and socioeconomic factors. Although this is a work in progress, the goal is to explore questions in the intersection between energy inequalities, socioeconomic conditions and dwelling characteristics.

Data and Software Availability

The data set with the spatial microsimulation at household level of the stock of houses for Scotland will be made available through Zenodo, and the code with the pipeline will be published in an open repository in GitHub (based in R).

Declaration of Generative AI in writing

No Generative AI tools were used for generating scientific content, research data, or substantive conclusions of this paper.

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